

Debating Agenda Items in Lithuanian Parliament: Politicization of policy issues in 1993-2021

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Abstract:

Introduction

Agenda-setting theory focuses on how issues get on the political agenda and what actors and factors play a role in setting agendas (see Cobb and Elder, 1971; Kingdon 1984; Jones and Baumgartner, 2005). Almost all researchers delve into issue framing as one of the most important aspects of agenda-setting theory since framing affects what aspects of a problem will be emphasized or blurred out in fighting for a space on the political agenda (see Schattschneider, 1961; Burgers et al. 2016; Eriksson, 2020). Additionally, framing gives an impetus for an audience to support the issues framed that meet its needs. Still, some issues are brought up by governing parties since they have agenda-setting power but are questioned by opposition to lessen their importance or put emphasis on different aspects of an issue to meet the needs of the audience they represent. The phenomenon of such controversy between the ruling majority and opposition is coined as issue politicization, which captured the attention of scholars focusing on the policy agenda-setting process.

The definition of politicization varies depending on the definition. Some scholars define it as contention over an issue (Riker, 1996), others characterize it as a conflict (Hutter and Gross, 2014; Urgo, 2018). Quite a few scientists focus on essential elements of politicization, such as polarization and salience (Brug et al., 2015; De Wile and Zürn, 2012; Hutter and Kriesi, 2019). Still, some scholars combine several elements as inevitable an issue to be politicized. Zuran argues that there is a need for a public setting in which united and authoritative decisions on a particular issue discussed are made, where a forum of diverse and polarizing opinions takes place, thereby politicizing issues (2019). Likewise, Green-Pedersen and Mortensen distinguish the role of the parliament in the politicization process, since there are certain procedures and practices to be followed that cannot be avoided or ignored, thus

creating a forum for opposing powers to question issues brought about by governing majority (2015). Still, if there are the same issues that matter to the governing or opposition party, a controversy may take over resolutions of an issue to be dealt with.

In the same vein, our article focuses on a multidimensional definition of politicization that encompasses several stages of politicization since, according to Palonen, it is a multi-faceted phenomenon that is the result of 'adversaries', 'anonymous forces', 'a matter of dispute', 'an object of defense' or 'an opportunity for something new' (Palonen, 2022). In addition, the scholar focuses on a venue where politicization occurs, aptly highlighting the importance of parliamentary debates (Palonen, 2017, 2022; also, Wiesner et al., 2017) where different interest meets and controversy over issues takes place between lawmakers in power and those dreaming of power.

This paper examines what topics grab the attention of different politicians and what issues are politicized the most than various issues put on the parliamentary agenda by governing parties. Scholars argue that there are different agendas. The agenda is managed by technocrats in a government and the political agenda is where the factual issue politicization occurs once an issue is put forward to parliamentary debates. As De Wilde puts it, politicization means the expanded authority of politicians in decision-making processes (2011; also, Palonen, 2021). Furthermore, parliamentary politicization can invoke more effective accountability of the government (Raunio, 2018) concerning polarizing issues within society and parliament itself. Therefore, the article focuses on the topics that are challenged by the opposition in the parliament of Lithuania from 1990 to 2020 and raise the most controversy by analyzing parliament transcripts and focusing on issues to which the opposition dedicate the most time voicing doubt, providing a critique of issues presented or pushing alternative pet solutions to the issues proposed.

Theoretical Background

The theory of agenda-setting theory focuses on how social issues are brought on the political agenda. Scholars explain that the struggle for a place on the political agenda takes place among different actors who put various emphasis on the same issue to make it salient by framing a matter for their own political gains (Kingdon, 1984; Rochefort and Cobb, 1993;

Baumgartner and Jones, 1993). Furthermore, Urgo observes that the abundant literature on agenda-setting theory highlights the role of party competition and framing as a central component of politicization. Furthermore, he contends that framing should be seen as part of the politicization process itself, despite the possibility that it might be exposed to political conflict (2018). Furthermore, in the literature on political agenda-setting, it goes almost without saying that putting issues on the agenda of public institutions politicizes them. Therefore, researchers note that this process is complex and encompasses several aspects, one of which is politicization. Palonen

Scholars submerged in the research of politicization by developing a commonly shared understanding of the concept. As Schattschneider described, politicization is a conflict whose absence depoliticizes a problem (1960). In addition, Riker defined politicization as the contestation of an issue that could be avoided by reaching a consensus on a contested issue (1996). Wiesner defines politicization 'as an active use of contingency, of rendering something contested or controversial' (Kari et al. 2019). Zürn, for example, believes that it can generally be defined as 'transferring something to the domain of public choice' (2019), while Hutter and Gross identify politicization as 'an expansion of the scope of conflicts within the political system' (2014). This idea is seconded by Urgo who maintains that increased salience of an issue is reached with an issue conflict among the parties (2018). After all, Green-Pedersen and Mortensen focus on the issue competition as a primary drive for politicization. They argue that parties are interconnected because some activities of a political party are influenced by the activities of other political parties. In addition, from an agenda-setting perspective, they contend that it is difficult for the parties to set the agenda disregarding the issues that other parties are talking about, as institutionalized discussions, such as parliaments, where the focus on the issues is inevitable (2015). Likewise, scholars argue that opposition parties are less responsible for party agendas than ruling parties and have the power to challenge the government when they focus on new issues. Governments are responsible for political solutions, but they face pressing problems, sometimes different from their original agenda (Green-Pedersen and Mortensen 2010, 2015). Furthermore, Seeberg aptly points out that the governing parties' strive for reelection combined with the opportunity of the opposing powers to set a political agenda pushes them to address the issues impelled by the opposition. As a result, some political changes are the upshot of the persistent emphasis on issues by the opposition (2013). Alternatively, van der Brug et al. developed a

conceptual framework of politicization consisting of two dimensions: polarization (contention among political players) and salience (intentional emphasis on certain issues) (2015). Likewise, De Wile and Zürn distinguish three main components to define politicization: salience, polarization, and actor expansion, which can be described accordingly as increased interest in an issue, abundance of diverse positions, and actors and audiences involved (2012, also see Hutter & Kriesi 2019). Furthermore, according to de Wile, politicization can be characterized by three groups: institutions, decision-making, and issues. Institutions, according to the scholar, maybe politicized over party politics through internal and external accountability mechanisms, while decision making through the rules, procedures, and practices which should be followed by institutions and, finally, issues by increasing emphasis on issues and a wide spectrum of opinions voiced (2011). At the same time, Wiesner presents the ‘multilevel and multistage model of politicization’. The scholar defines the first stage as related to naming an issue as political, while the second one is related to the outset of issue salience and entrance to public venues, and the final stage is related to the issues linkage with different public arenas (Palonen et al. 2019).

Discussing politicization, Palonen also notes that there are no phenomena that cannot be a target of politics as it becomes political because of interpretations made by political actors or audiences (2022). Furthermore, scholar contends that politicization works in a way to provoke controversy over issues on the parliamentary agenda that in some ways had not previously been discussed. On the other hand, Palonen focuses on the definition of politicization by dividing it into several stages. In conceptualizing politicization, the scholar classifies five styles of politicization, ‘parliamentary government acting in the presence of adversaries’, ‘dissensus procedure as a guarantee for opposing points of view’, ‘debate *pro et contra* [for and against] as a criterion of parliamentary speaking’, ‘freedom of parliamentarians from dependence on arbitrary powers’, and ‘parliamentary time as a subtext of politics’ (2021). Succinctly, it can be presented as procedural and rhetorical forms of politicization in parliament. The first is related to putting issues on the agenda and the latter concerns debating issues on the agenda or exploring their strengths and weaknesses.

Methods

Results

Fig X. Only debates on legislative bills (excluded are all ceremonial debates, discussions, government hours, interpellations, declarations and similar MPs' speeches/activities on the floor).

Fig X. Only debates on the introductory stage.

Fig X. Only debates on the consideration stage.

Fig X. Only debates on the passage stage.

Fig X.

Fig X.

Conclusions

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